

**THE REPRESENTATION OF MACRO AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF BILINGUAL
DICTIONARIES**

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Annotation: In this thesis, it will be presented the mega structure of bilingual dictionaries. Dictionaries are indicators or mirrors of a country's cultural, social, scientific and technological development. I highlighted macro and micro structure of bilingual dictionaries. It is essential to use dictionaries properly in learning a foreign language.

Keywords: dictionary, bilingual, macrostructure, microstructure, megastructure, metalexigraphy, front matter, back matter, lemma

Bilingual dictionaries serve as invaluable resources for language learners, translators, and individuals seeking to navigate the complexities of multilingual communication. These dictionaries offer a comprehensive compilation of words, phrases, and their translations, enabling users to bridge linguistic gaps and enhance their language proficiency. According to the scholar Parman Singh, dictionary structure is the component parts of a dictionary that presents the overall design of a dictionary. To present the structure of a dictionary in metalexigraphy there are three terms, which are commonly used. These are megastructure, macrostructure and microstructure. The relation between these three terms will be realizing with the discussion of dictionary structure. As for him the overall architectural realization of the structure of a dictionary can be presented with the help of following architecture:

To fully comprehend the functionality and organization of bilingual dictionaries, it is essential to explore both their macro and micro structure. “Almost all dictionaries consist of four different parts under term of megastructure: “before the dictionary text, inside the dictionary text, after the dictionary text, and beyond the dictionary text”. While the first three levels of structure can be observed in all types of dictionaries, the last one just suitable to the bilingual type.” [1] “Heming Young offered to collect “before the dictionary text (front matter)” and “after the dictionary text (back matter)” under one general heading “outside matter structure” while the paradigmatic and syntagmatic structures “inside the dictionary text” will be discussed in “macrostructure” and “microstructure”. . However, Jackson’s structural division is a bit different, he describes the

structure of dictionaries from the two perspective of its “macro structure”, and “microstructure”. The former consists of the front matter, the body, and the appendices, the last covers the arrangement of the information within the entries. Front matter of the dictionary may include some or all of the following things:

- Selection of cover design.
- Production of the title page with the information regarding the editor(s), publication and publisher.
- Table of contents.
- It usually includes an introduction or preface, explaining the innovations and characteristics of the edition concerned.
- Introduction to the dictionary outlining and the editorial principles followed in the work.
- General information about the language.
- If it is a dialect dictionary it should contain the map of the dialect to locate the area.
- Information about the convention made and followed in the dictionary.
- Provide the list of abbreviations used in compilation of the dictionary.
- If possible there should be brief note on the orthography because dictionary will be a powerful influence on standardizing the orthography. It is essential to note that the front matter of the any dictionary explains style , structure and content of the dictionary, besides it is a user’s guide and key to the dictionary.

As to back matter of the dictionary, the back matter may include some or all of the following articles:

- Some dictionary includes the tables for the numbers, days of the week, months of the year, seasons etc.
- It may include the list of prefixes and suffixes.
- Some dictionary informs the system of weights and measures, information about military ranks, chemical elements, technical terms, legal and constitutional term etc.
- It will be useful to give a table of proper nouns-personal names, family names, place names in the back matter rather than including them in the dictionary proper.
- Some dictionaries include special appendixes for special sets of words, include list of semantic domains, list of irregular words.
- Comprehensive dictionary may provide the list of frequent proverbs and quotations.
- If some error is realized after compiling the dictionary, the list is included in the back matter.

It is also called an errata or correction chit.

- The back matter should also contain the bibliography.

It should also contain the list of previously published dictionaries, especially if it cited or incorporated in the present work. The back matter of dictionaries not only contain linguistic information but also encyclopedic data on account of the size or scope of a dictionary. “The internal structure of the entries, called the MICROSTRUCTURE of the dictionary. Furthermore, the entries must themselves be arranged in a particular order in accordance with the purpose and intended use of the dictionary. This aspect, the MACROSTRUCTURE of the dictionary.” [2] According to Sh. Nashirova a bilingual dictionary is a mega system with internal nodes, which by its architectural composition consists of **mega-, macro -, micro-, multi-, and medio** systems. A megastructure is a basic structure (framework structure) of a dictionary, which completely covers everything from the dictionary cover and title to the introduction, corpus, and appendices.

Macrostructure is considered the core of the dictionary; the dictionary consists of a set of articles (dictionary corpus, dictionary). It determines the order of the dictionary units – lemmas in the dictionary. **Microstructure** is a dictionary entry based on the title *word* and its semantics, tags, and links. The microstructure of the dictionary reflects the structure of the article. **Multistructure** is a component of a dictionary entry. The title word, grammatical and phonetic marks, lexical meaning, semantics, illustrative reference, and other parts. **Mediostructure**-parts are typical for the construction of ideographic and electronic educational dictionaries, attached to the general vocabulary material in order to achieve volumetric compactness. As to Ch. Lehmann, “The dictionary as a whole has a framing structure which comprises a set of main sections that correspond to the chapters of a book. A subset of these sections – mostly only one – comprises an entry list. The structure of each of these sections is a macrostructure (or the macrostructure of the dictionary). Each of the entries in a macrostructure has an internal structure of its own, which is the microstructure of the entries of that list (thus, if the dictionary contains only one word list, the microstructure of the dictionary).”

“The macrostructure is the flexible structure because it is always possible to add or subtract an entry word without destroying the quality of the word list. The headwords represent the particular selection of vocabulary and other items that the editor(s) has decided merit inclusion according to the size, nature and purpose of the dictionary. It ranges from reasonably comprehensive, as in large unabridged works, to highly selective, as in small pocket dictionaries. Depending on size and user, single-volume synchronic dictionaries tend to emphasize the central core vocabulary of contemporary standard usage of a language. It focuses on new words, senses and on general technical terms from administration and technology. This flexibility helps in compiling subject or special dictionaries. The microstructure customarily provides information on the form, meaning and use of the lemma. Formal information may include spelling and pronunciation, base and inflected forms and syntactic category. Semantic information includes definitions or explanations of literal and figurative, denotative and connotative meanings. These may take the form of synonyms or near-synonyms, paraphrases or formulae. They are usually supplemented by paradigmatic information on lexical fields involving synonyms, antonyms, or hyponyms; by syntagmatic information on lexical collocation, grammatical colligation and complementation, and on use in idioms, proverbs, and other fixed phrases and chunks; and by pragmatic information marking on register, frequency, currency, style, status, and subject area. They may be complemented by pictorial illustrations, authentic, adapted and constructed textual examples and usage notes.”[3]

We described structure of English-Uzbek bilingual dictionaries like that: front matter and back matter under outside matter structure, entry texts of the dictionary (the body) under microstructure and outside matter and microstructure under macrostructure. For example, the mega-content "English-Uzbek dictionary" by Sh. Botayev includes the following parts:

1. Cover and title of the dictionary.
2. Dictionary annotation.
3. Foreword to the English-Uzbek, Uzbek-English Dictionary
4. Educational methodical device called "The structure of the dictionary and the procedure for using it":
 - 4.1. Structure of the dictionary.
 - 4.2. Meaning characteristics of words in the dictionary.

- 4.3. The arrangement of word meanings.
- 4.4. Phraseology in the dictionary.
- 4.5. Grammatical characteristics of words.
- 4.6. Pronunciation and accent.
- 5. Conditional abbreviations and additional information.
 - 5.1. List of English abbreviations.
 - 5.2. List of Uzbek abbreviations.
 - 5.3. Uzbek and English alphabet.
- 6. Vocabulary corpus..
 - 6.1. English-Uzbek dictionary.
 - 6.2. Uzbek-English dictionary.
- 7. Applications:
 - 7.1. The List of Irregular Verbs
 - 7.2. The List of Geographical Names
 - 7.3. Abbreviations.

The microstructure of bilingual dictionary means the arrangement of the information within the entries. According to Yong Hemin's description microstructure is "the lemma article (entry) starts with the headword, which is followed by its orthographical, phonological, morphological, syntactical, pragmatic and, most important of all, semantic descriptions". It usually ends with etymology, which is found especially in unabridged bilingual dictionaries. Sequence of the lemma article can be diagrammed as follows:

headword → pronunciation → part of speech → inflections → grammatical, register and other codes → definitions → illustrations → word origin.

"The type and extend of information within an entry will vary according to the kind of headword, but will typically include like following ones in English-Uzbek dictionaries: spelling, word class, inflections, senses, usage sign, translation or definition, examples/ illustrations, run-ons, etymology. However, in English- Uzbek dictionaries origin of words are not taken into consideration.

All in all, bilingual dictionaries serve as indispensable tools for language learners and translators, providing a wealth of linguistic information. Understanding the macro and micro structures of these dictionaries is crucial for making the most of their resources. The macro structure establishes the overall organization and accessibility, while the micro structure offers detailed information and contextual guidance. From the perspective of its "macrostructure", there are potentially three parts to a dictionary: the front matter, the body, and back matter (the appendices) while the microstructure provides information on the form, meaning and use of the lemma. By navigating both the macro and micro levels, users can effectively utilize bilingual dictionaries to expand their language skills and navigate the complexities of multilingual communication.

Reference:

1. Jumanova Orzigul Sa'dulla qizi LEXICOGRAPHICAL DESCRIPTION OF ENGLISH-UZBEK BILINGUAL DICTIONARIES' MACROSTRUCTURE.
2. A Handbook of Lexicography: The Theory and Practice of Dictionary-Making Bo Svensen. 20-21
3. Parman Singh DICTIONARY AND ITS STRUCTURE .ANUSILANA - A Refereed Journal, Published Bi Monthly

4. NASHIROVA SHAXNOZA BURIYEVNA “IKKI TILLI O‘QUV LUG‘ATLARDA KO‘P MA‘NOLI SO‘ZLARNING LEKSIKOGRAFIK TALQINI” Monografiya QARSHI– 2023
5. www.christianlehmann.eu
6. Bo‘tayev Sh. Inglizcha-o‘zbekcha, o‘zbekcha-inglizcha lug‘at (80000 so‘z). “O‘qituvchi” nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, Toshkent, 2013, – B.5.
7. Yong H. and Peng J. Bilingual Lexicography from Communicative Perspective. - Amsterdam/Philadelphia, 2007